

Characterization of CdS/Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe Films

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Abstract

A method of forming a compound film can be fabricated by using the cadmium sulphide (CdS) compound and cadmium zinc telluride (Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe) compounds with the ways of coating the pastes on the glass substrates and sintering the films in a suitable atmosphere. The structural properties of (CdS and Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe) compound powders were analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. The electrical properties of the films were investigated by photoconductivity measurement. The n-CdS/p-Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe heterojunction solar cells were fabricated on glass substrates by screen printing method and by sintering method. By using the same technique, the second layer of p-type Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe layers was printed on the n-type CdS layers. After coating with the carbon conductive paste on the p-type Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe layers, silver electrode layers were applied on both of the carbon layers and the boundary of CdS layers. The obtained CdS/Cd_{0.96}Zn_{0.04}Te/C/Ag, CdS/Cd_{0.8}Zn_{0.2}Te/C/Ag, CdS/Cd_{0.4}Zn_{0.6}Te/C/Ag films were measured with I-V characteristic measurement. After measuring the films with I-V method, the short circuit current, the open circuit voltage, the fill factor and the efficiency were determined.

Keywords: screen printing method, Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe film

Introduction

Polycrystalline Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe films and its window layer of CdS were successfully utilized in the fabrication of solar cell structure (Alessandro, 2002). There are a variety of deposition techniques that have been used for the growth of Group II-VI compound semiconductor films such as chemical bath deposition, sol-gel techniques, MOCVD, sputtering, electrochemical deposition and screen printing technique (Burgelman, 2001). Among them a method of screen printing with sintering is one of the cheapest and convenient techniques for fabrication of these films. The objective of the present study is to deposit Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe layers on CdS layers by screen printing technique. I-V characteristics measurement was carried out and calculation of solar cell parameters were discussed (Bube, 1960).

Experiment

The procedure consists of sequentially depositing several layers onto a glass substrate, configured as glass/CdS/CZT/C/Ag layers. Cadmium sulphide was fabricated by using the temperature controlled furnace in open air and cadmium zinc telluride was fabricated by using the temperature controlled vacuum chamber.

Screen Printing Technique

Screen-printing, previously known as silk-screening is a printmaking technique that creates a sharp-edged image using a stencil. The tools are 8" × 11" wooden frame, 2" rubber squeegee, masking tape, glass and printing board and mesh counter as shown in Figure 1. The important screen printing parameters are the viscosity of the paste, the mesh number of the screen and the snap-off distance between the screen and the substrate. In the present work, the mesh number of the silk screen is 150 meshes per inch and the snap-off distance is 0.7 cm.

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Figure 1. Tools for screen printing (a) Wooden frame (b) Squeegee (c) Glass and printing board.

Composition and Structure of Vacuum System

The instrument (TOKUDA, JAPAN) is composed of four sections as shown in Figure 2. These four sections are the vacuum chamber, the rotary pump, the electrical system and temperature controller system. The vacuum chamber is mounted on the top of the cabinet and the two systems stay beside the cabinet.

Figure 2. Photograph of Vacuum System

Preparation of CdS Films

CdS compound was prepared by taking a 0.5 M aqueous solution of thiourea and 0.5M aqueous solution of cadmium chloride as starting solutions. To obtain the solution, thiourea and cadmium chloride powders were firstly weighed according to their molecular weight ratios, and then mixed with distilled water and stirred the powders to dissolve completely. The resultant solution was heated on the oven by ranging the temperature from 300°C to 400°C until the solution was completely dried to form orange powder and it took about 45 minutes for the entire process. When the solution was heated the following reaction took place.

Then, the dry weighted CdS and CdCl₂ powders were mixed before the binder was added. Then, a few drops of PG were added to form the paste. The prepared paste was screen printed on borosilicate glass substrates. The prepared films were dried at 120°C for one hour in the atmosphere. After that, the three films were sintered in different temperature as 500°C, 600°C and 690°C for 3 minutes in the atmosphere. After cooling down to room temperature, CdS films were obtained.

Figure 3. Photographs of (a) CdS film at 500°C (b) CdS film at 600°C (c) CdS film at 690°C

Preparation of $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ Films (Composition of $x=0.04, 0.2$ and 0.6)

For preparation of $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ compounds, cadmium metals, zinc powders and tellurium powders of high purity were used. Firstly high purity cadmium metals were ground by a file and then cadmium powders were obtained. The obtained cadmium powder, zinc powder and tellurium powder were weighed in line with the stoichiometric formula $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ (where $x = 0.04, 0.2, 0.6$), and they were crushed with propylene glycol for one hour. The three obtained powders were dried at 120°C for one hour and thermally heated at 600°C for one hour in the temperature controlled vacuum chamber. After cooling down the temperature to room temperature, the three $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ compounds were obtained.

To prepare $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ pastes, $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ compounds powder and zinc chloride ($ZnCl_2$) powder were thoroughly mixed and then a few drops of PG were added. The weight of $ZnCl_2$ was only 10% of the weight of $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ powders. $ZnCl_2$ was used as a flux and PG as a viscous agent. Then the pastes were applied to the borosilicate glass substrates under the screen printing method to form coating layers. The prepared films were dried at 120°C for one hour in the vacuum chamber. Then the films were sintered at 550°C for 15 minutes in the temperature controlled furnace in vacuum. The obtained $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ films were shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Photographs of (a) $Cd_{0.96}Zn_{0.04}Te$ film (b) $Cd_{0.8}Zn_{0.2}Te$ film (c) $Cd_{0.4}Zn_{0.6}Te$ film

CdS/ $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ Films Preparation

Firstly, the prepared CdS pastes were applied onto the three glass substrates by using screen-printing method. Then they were dried at 120°C for one hour in air and sintered at 690°C for 3 minutes in air. Next, $Cd_{0.96}Zn_{0.04}Te$, $Cd_{0.8}Zn_{0.2}Te$ and $Cd_{0.4}Zn_{0.6}Te$ pastes were applied on the above CdS sintered layer with the same method, then dried again at 120°C for 1 hour and sintered at 550°C for 15 minutes in temperature controlled vacuum chamber. Next, Carbon conductive paste was applied on the p-type $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ layers to obtain an electricity collecting electrode. Further, the silver conducting grease was applied on the carbon layer and also applied on boundary of CdS layer to form conducting area. Finally, negative terminal of CdS and positive terminal of $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ were soldered with copper wires as an electrode by using silver conducting grease. Finally, $CdS/Cd_{0.96}Zn_{0.04}Te/C/Ag$, $CdS/Cd_{0.8}Zn_{0.2}Te/C/Ag$ and $CdS/Cd_{0.4}Zn_{0.6}Te/C/Ag$ films were obtained and shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. A schematic sectional view of a Group II-VI compound semiconductor solar cell of n-CdS/p- $\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{Te}$ type

Figure 6. Photographs of $\text{CdS}/\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{Te}/\text{C}/\text{Ag}$ films after electrode

Results and Discussion

Surface Morphology of CdS Films

By analyzing the three images, it can be revealed that CdS films are composed by spherical-shaped densely packed particles in Figure 7(a) and 7(b) but in Figure 7(c) it is composed of non-uniformed structure. SEM images of CdS films at 500°C and 600°C indicate that these films have poor crystalline structure than that of CdS film at 690°C .

Surface Morphology of $\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{Te}$ Films

From Figure 8, all the films are adherent crack free form and grained microstructure with small crystallite sizes. It is assumed that these are spread uniformly on the surface areas. Based on these three figures, it appears that grain size decreases with increasing zinc content in the films.

Figure 7. SEM image of CdS films on glass substrate at (a)500°C (b) 600°C (c) 690°C

Figure 8. SEM image of $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ films on glass substrate at 550°C

XRD Analysis of CdS Compound

The XRD patterns of CdS compound were recorded with different diffraction peaks corresponding to different plane as shown in Figure 9. There exist CdS peaks of (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), (103) and (112) planes. The highest peak and the peak positions are in good agreement with the hexagonal cadmium sulphide. The prominent peak is (101) plane and the crystallite size is estimated as 52.79 nm from FWHM of this peak.

XRD Analysis of $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ Compound

Figure 10, 11 and 12 show the XRD patterns of $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$ compounds at various compositions of (where $x = 0.04, 0.2$ and 0.6). XRD analysis shows that all the compounds have highly oriented crystalline with cubic structure.

All the peaks heights and peak positions are in good agreement with library file of XRD machine. It is found that all three samples exhibited preferential orientation along the (111) plane. These traces confirm the formation of compound $Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe$. It can be also found that a decrease in crystallite size is observed with the increase of zinc content in these compounds. The crystallite sizes was calculated and shown in Table 1.

Figure 9. XRD Pattern of CdS Compound

Figure 10. XRD Pattern of Cd_{0.96}Zn_{0.04}Te Compound

Figure 11. XRD Pattern of Cd_{0.8}Zn_{0.2}Te Compound

Figure 12. XRD Pattern of Cd_{0.4}Zn_{0.6}Te Compound

Calculation of Crystallite Size

The crystallite size was calculated from XRD peak broadening using Scherrer formula. The crystallite sizes were listed in Table 1.

The Scherrer's equation is

$$G = \frac{0.91 \times \lambda (\text{\AA})}{\text{FWHM (rad)} \times \cos \theta} \quad (2)$$

where, G = Crystallite size

λ = X-ray wavelength (1.54056 \AA)

θ = Bragg's diffraction angle

FWHM = Full-wave half maximum

Table 1. The Values of Crystallite Size

Types of Compound	Plane	2 θ value (degree)	FWHM (degree)	Crystallite size (nm)
Cd _{0.96} Zn _{0.04} Te	(111)	23.839	0.094	87.29
Cd _{0.8} Zn _{0.2} Te	(111)	23.833	0.094	87.29
Cd _{0.4} Zn _{0.6} Te	(111)	24.535	0.201	40.88
CdS	(101)	28.320	0.157	52.79

Photoconductivity of CdS Film

The decay of photoconductivity with time at room temperature for CdS film is shown in Figure 13. Photoconductivity of CdS film decreases abruptly when light is turned off and after a few seconds, it decreases steadily with respect to time. It is noted that the decay of photoconductivity for the sintered film of CdS is fast and high photosensitivity. Thus it can be concluded that CdS film is suitable for fabrication of photo detector and window layer for solar cells.

Photoconductivity of Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe Films

The decay of photoconductivity with time at room temperature for Cd_{0.96}Zn_{0.04}Te, Cd_{0.8}Zn_{0.2}Te and Cd_{0.4}Zn_{0.6}Te films are shown in Figure 14, 15 and 16. Figure 14 reveals that when light falls on the film, the decay of photoconductivity decreases slowly and steadily after a few second. When light is turned off, it decreases slowly and steadily with respect to time. In Figure 15, when light is turned on the film, the decay of photoconductivity decreases abruptly and then steadily after a few second. When light is turned off, it decreases abruptly and after some time it is almost constant. Figure 16 indicates that when light is turned on the film, the decay of photoconductivity decreases slightly until the light is turned off. And then the conductivity decreases after a few seconds and it decreases steadily with respect to time. By analyzing the three figures, the decay of photoconductivity of Cd_{0.8}Zn_{0.2}Te film is faster and its photosensitivity is better than that of other films.

Figure 13. Variation of photoconductivity of CdS film with time

Figure 14. Variation of photoconductivity of $\text{Cd}_{0.96}\text{Zn}_{0.04}\text{Te}$ film with time

Figure 15. Variation of photoconductivity of $\text{Cd}_{0.8}\text{Zn}_{0.2}\text{Te}$ film with time

Figure 16. Variation of photoconductivity of $\text{Cd}_{0.4}\text{Zn}_{0.6}\text{Te}$ film with time

Results from I-V Measurement

The experimental setup consists of $5\text{M}\Omega$ potentiometer and two multimeters. The full current-voltage curves have been measured by turning the potentiometer. The open circuit voltage and short circuit current are obtained from the x and y intercepts, respectively. The measurements have been taken outside and measured under illumination by sunlight. The full I-V graphs for sunlight-illuminated $\text{CdS}/\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{Te}$ films are shown in Figure 17. Open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), short-circuit current (I_{sc}), efficiency (η) and fill factor (FF) are listed in Table 2. The maximum values of V_{oc} and I_{sc} are found in $\text{Cd}_{0.96}\text{Zn}_{0.04}\text{Te}/\text{CdS}$ cell. The maximum value of fill factor is attained by $\text{Cd}_{0.8}\text{Zn}_{0.2}\text{Te}/\text{CdS}$ cell. It can be found that the efficiency of the cells decreases with an increase in zinc concentration of the cells.

Table 2. Photovoltaic Parameters of $\text{CdS}/\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{Te}$ Cells

Types of Cell	V_{oc} (V)	I_{sc} (mA)	P_{max} (mW)	FF	η (%)
$\text{Cd}_{0.96}\text{Zn}_{0.04}\text{Te}/\text{CdS}$	0.49	0.42	0.14	0.70	0.33
$\text{Cd}_{0.8}\text{Zn}_{0.2}\text{Te}/\text{CdS}$	0.43	0.39	0.12	0.73	0.28
$\text{Cd}_{0.4}\text{Zn}_{0.6}\text{Te}/\text{CdS}$	0.32	0.35	0.08	0.67	0.17

Figure 17. I-V curve of CdS/Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe films under sunlight illumination

Conclusion

Growth of CdS/Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe (where $x = 0.04, 0.2$ and 0.6) photovoltaic devices are fabricated by screen printing technique followed by sintering process. CdS compound has hexagonal structure and its peak heights and peak positions are in good agreement with XRD library file. From XRD analysis of Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe compounds, the highest peak of (111) plane confirmed that they have cubic zinblende structure and their peak positions are in good agreement with XRD library file. From these results, it can be concluded that the crystallite size decreases with increase in zinc concentration. CdS film at 690°C is the finest so it is chosen for the window layer of CdS based Cd_{1-x}Zn_xTe film solar cells. Finally CdS/Cd_{0.96}Zn_{0.04}Te, CdS/Cd_{0.8}Zn_{0.2}Te and CdS/Cd_{0.4}Zn_{0.6}Te films are successfully fabricated. After coating with carbon and silver conductive grease, I-V measurements are carried out. The maximum values of open-circuit voltage (0.49V), short-circuit current (0.42mA) and the efficiency (0.33%) are obtained for the CdS/Cd_{0.96}Zn_{0.04}Te films. The maximum value of fill factor (0.73) is obtained for the CdS/Cd_{0.8}Zn_{0.2}Te film.

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